

MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING IN SCHOOLS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the issues of organizing multicultural education and upbringing of school-age children in Uzbekistan from the perspective of analyzing the requirements of national legislation, state standards in the field of public education and the content of educational programs. Tolerance in Uzbekistan, which is a multicultural country, is a necessary quality for a modern schoolchild. Therefore, the state is taking measures to educate children into a harmoniously developed personality by introducing them to their native culture and the culture of other peoples, instilling respect for people, forming the foundations of tolerance, understanding and acceptance of universal human values.*

Keywords: *school, upbringing, tolerance, multicultural education, nation, nationality, culture, language.*

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a multinational country. Representatives of more than 130 nations and nationalities live in the republic. According to statistical information from the Open Data Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with reference to data from the State Statistics Committee, in 2023, over 80 percent of the population of Uzbekistan are Uzbeks, more than 10 percent are representatives of other peoples of Central Asia (Tajiks, Kazakhs, Karakalpaks, Kyrgyz, Turkmen and others.). Russians and other Slavic peoples make up 10 percent of the republic's population.

Within the framework of UNESCO, more than seventy international documents and conventions on tolerance have been adopted. On November 16, 1995, at the 28th session of the UNESCO General Conference, the Declaration of Principles of Tolerance was adopted, calling for interethnic harmony and interreligious tolerance to preserve peace. The declaration found a wide response among the public of Uzbekistan. This date began to be celebrated as the International Day of Tolerance.

In our difficult times, interethnic harmony and interfaith tolerance sometimes play a decisive role in maintaining peace and stability, which are a necessary condition for sustainable development. This is the kind of friendly atmosphere that reigns in Uzbekistan. There are 2,238 religious organizations operating in the country, almost 140 national cultural centers working in the interests of the nations and nationalities living here, respect for their languages is ensured, and conditions are created for their development. In general education schools of our Republic, education is conducted in 7 languages using textbooks published on the basis of state educational standards. Television and radio broadcasts are conducted in 12 languages, and newspapers and magazines are published in 14 languages.

The education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan deals with a complex, ethnically diverse, culturally and mentally diverse student population. Their composition is formed from various layers of society, represented by various ethnic groups, focused on various cultural values.

The need for tolerant coexistence of large and small ethnic and national groups gives rise to the need multicultural upbringing and education as an important social and pedagogical principle.

The term “multicultural education” is not of domestic origin. It is a copy of the concept (“multicultural education”) formed in Western culture in the 1970s. The International Encyclopedia of Education defines it as “a pedagogical process in which two or more cultures differing in language, ethnicity, nationality, or race are represented.”

A student’s tolerance reflects his attitude towards the teacher, school, education, parents, and the surrounding social and subject environment. Thus, pedagogical relations dictate the need to distinguish different types of tolerance. At the same time, the peculiarity of a tolerant attitude is that it is always a friendly attitude. The types of tolerance that reflect the directions of educational work can be important: ideological, confessional, tolerance of students in labor, aesthetic education.

Awareness of the importance of multicultural education, tolerance, and dialogue of cultures is reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws “On the State Language” and “On Education,” as well as the Concept of State Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations.

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan All citizens are guaranteed the same rights and freedoms, including freedom of conscience, the right to education, equality before the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, social origin, social status.

For these purposes, the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendly Relations with Foreign Countries has been created and operates under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which consistently implements state policy to ensure interethnic harmony and tolerance in society.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the State Language”, the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the Uzbek language. Its status does not infringe on the constitutional rights of nations and nationalities living on the territory of the republic in using their native language. The Republic of Uzbekistan ensures respect for the languages of all nations and nationalities living on its territory and creates conditions for the development of these languages. Citizens are given the right to freely choose the language of instruction. The Republic of Uzbekistan provides on its territory the receipt of general secondary education in the state language of the republic, as well as in Russian, Karakalpak, Tajik, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen languages and in the languages of other nationalities living compactly in the republic.

Thus, on the territory of modern Uzbekistan, other languages are also used in a number of regions. For example, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Karakalpak is also the official language. In the Sokh district of the Fergana region, where the majority of the population is ethnic Tajiks, there are 24 schools, 2 lyceums and 2 colleges with Tajik as the language of instruction. Schools with Tajik language of instruction operate in Surkhandarya, Samarkand, Bukhara and Namangan regions. In the Tashkent and Navoi regions, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, there are schools with Kazakh language of instruction. About 170 thousand Turkmens live in the Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. More than 8 thousand children of Turkmen

nationality are studying in 46 schools where the language of instruction is Turkmen. In 24 schools, education is conducted entirely in the Turkmen language. More than 18 thousand ethnic Kyrgyz children study in 56 secondary Kyrgyz schools.

In 2021, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation launched a joint ten-year project “Class”, which involves Russian teachers teaching the Russian language and subjects in Russian in order to improve the quality of its teaching in Uzbekistan. Part of this project was the development of a new educational and methodological complex in the Russian language for grades 2-11 in schools with Uzbek as the language of instruction. The textbooks have been developed in accordance with the new educational program for studying Russian as a foreign language. A joint team of leading Russian and Uzbek authors was involved in the creation of the methodology.

The operators of the project were the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A.I.Herzen, International Education Center "Interdom" named after E.D.Stasova, Research Institute for Studying Problems and Determining Prospects of Public Education named after A.Avloni.

In addition, the basic principles in the field of education contained in the Law “On Education” are the inadmissibility of discrimination in the field of education, the introduction of national and universal values in education and upbringing, the humanistic, democratic nature of education and upbringing. Everyone is guaranteed equal rights to receive education regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, personal and social status.

Much attention to the implementation of one of the priorities of state policy - ensuring interethnic harmony and tolerance in society, educating young people in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, is given in the Concept of state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 15, 2019 No. UP-5876, as well as the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026, approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 No. PD-134.

The concept of “tolerance” has firmly entered the education system in schools of Uzbekistan, starting from the first grade, where during the “Education” and “Class Hour” lessons, special attention is paid to the formation of a multi-ethnic culture.

The basis for programmatic and methodological support for the formation of social and pedagogical conditions and pedagogical activities to cultivate a culture of tolerance in schools are curricula and teaching and methodological plans developed on the basis of the State educational standards of general secondary and secondary special education, approved by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6 2017 No. 187.

In particular, in the 2020-2021 academic year, a new subject “Education” was introduced into the curriculum of secondary schools, which has a spiritual and educational orientation, incorporating courses such as “National Idea”, “Ethics”, “History of Religions”, “Sense of National pride.” Educational and thematic plans for this subject contain lessons aimed at instilling in students kindness, respect, friendship, universal values, the formation of high spirituality, the components of which are patriotism, ideological immunity, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, and hard work.

From primary school, the curriculum includes the topics “Uzbekistan is a multinational state”, “Respect for the language - respect for the people”, “Success is in unity”, “Together we are

strong”, “Everyone is equal before the law”, “Humanity”, “Friendship is the highest quality,” “Charity is a human virtue.”

In teaching the topics, advanced technologies and teaching methods are used, such as Project-Based Learning, Interest-Based Teaching, Role Model, Situation Analysis and others.

In addition to the subject “Education”, elements of instilling tolerance are present in the lessons of “Class Hour” (“Friendship is a priceless gift”, “Tashkent is the city of friendship”, “Tolerance”, “Learning languages - we get to know peoples”, etc.).

Every year in November, in schools of Uzbekistan, as part of the “Week of Tolerance”, events are held (classes, exhibitions, competitions) dedicated to the International Day of Tolerance - November 16, and the anniversaries of representatives of cultures of many nations - the Kazakh poet Abay Kunabaev, are regularly celebrated, Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov, Russian poet Alexander Pushkin, Belarusian poet Yakub Kolas, Turkmen poet Magtymguly, Tatar writer Musa Jalil and many others.

Thus, the measures taken help students cultivate delicacy, tolerance, respect for other people’s opinions, the ability to perceive people of other nations and religions and resolve conflicts with dignity, and also contribute to expanding their worldview.

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